

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

YEAR: 2024

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL

ISSN: 3048-7951

**A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER-REVIEWED
& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL**

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Editor-in-Chief
AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL
(ISSN: 3048-7951)
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India

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The paper has been assigned the DOI link: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21185732>

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